

Municipal Investments and Fine Particulate Matter (PM2.5) in Portugal (2019-2025)

Abstract

This article analyses the spatial distribution and temporal evolution of fine particulate matter (PM2.5) across Portugal's 308 municipalities from 2019 to 2025, exploring its associations with local economic and cultural investment patterns. By integrating satellite-derived air quality data with municipal financial indicators from the Portuguese National Institute of Statistics, distinct PM2.5 exposure trajectories are identified through k-means clustering. Subsequently, Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) and mixed hierarchical classification uncover structural correspondences between these pollution profiles and municipalities' economic and cultural configurations. Investment indicators from 2024—the most recent consolidated fiscal year—were used as proxies for medium-term municipal strategies. The results reveal that PM2.5 exposure follows a triadic pattern in Portugal aligned with capital competence regimes: (i) peripheral municipalities with low emissions and limited investment capacity; (ii) intermediate zones with moderate pollution and structurally constrained investment; and (iii) urban and coastal hubs where high economic and cultural capital coincide with the most persistent pollution burdens. These spatial correspondences show that PM2.5 pollution in Portugal is a structurally embedded externality of territorially differentiated development strategies, calling for ecological-economic governance frameworks that integrate cultural and territorial dimensions into mitigation policies.

Keywords: PM2.5, pollution, economic investment, cultural investment, capital externalities.

1. Introduction

The unintended social costs generated by economic activities, usually remain unaccounted for in market transactions but have profound implications for society and the environment (Stiglitz 2025; Dasgupta 2024). Building on this foundation, William D. Nordhaus, further developed the analysis of capital externalities demonstrating how industrial investments and economic growth can generate negative externalities—such as air pollution and greenhouse gas emissions—that impose significant long-term costs on societies, costs that are often not internalised by the polluters themselves (Barrage and Nordhaus 2024; Nordhaus 2024). A key concern from these perspectives is the estimation of the social cost of carbon – as an equivalent measure of greenhouse gases and air pollution mitigations-, crucial for setting global market prices, industry responsibilities, national obligations, and environmental policies. This approach usually focuses on processes on a macro level, treating countries and industries as the main agents. As a result, it overlooks the micro-geographical patterns of air pollution within countries, and how different economic, cultural and political investments are related with these patterns (Gomez, Miño, Hojman, et al. 2025; Gomez and Miño 2025).

Among the most prominent negative externalities generated by modern economies are those associated with air pollution, such as particulate matter (PM). Particulate matter comprises a complex mixture of extremely small particles and liquid droplets suspended in the air, including PM2.5— fine particles with a diameter of 2.5 micrometres or less—which are especially hazardous due to their ability to penetrate deep into the respiratory tract (Luo et al. 2024; “WHO” 2024). The public health consequences of prolonged exposure to high levels of PM2.5 are severe, with robust evidence linking such exposure to increased morbidity and mortality from respiratory and cardiovascular diseases (Dockery 2022; Tran et al. 2025; Dockery and

Pope 2020). The prevalence and intensity of PM pollution are closely linked to patterns of economic development, industrial activity, and the concentration of population and infrastructure in large urban centres (Nori-Sarma et al. 2024; Alam, Karim, and Zaman 2025; Worratanakit et al. 2025). That is capital development and urban expansion, while drivers of economic growth, result in physical objectifications such as atmospheric pollutants, which disproportionately impact communities located in or near major industrial and transport hubs.

An underexplored relationship about capital externalities concerns the multiple correspondences between mixed investments—economic and cultural—at the sub-national level and the co-located emissions of PM_{2.5}. This line of inquiry becomes particularly relevant when approached from a relational sociological perspective, which posits that the unequal distribution and accumulation of capital competences—whether economic or cultural—not only structures opportunities and life chances within the social space (Bourdieu 1989; Atkinson 2017; Pereira 2024), but also produces objectified consequences for localised populations in the physical space (Gomez, Miño, Pereira, et al. 2025; Gomez, Miño, Hojman, et al. 2025; Gomez and Miño 2025; Pereira 2019, 2024). These structural effects broaden the analytical scope of classical approaches to capital externalities. Against this backdrop, the central question addressed in this article is as follows: *How are the temporal trajectories of PM_{2.5} exposure (2019—2025) spatially distributed across Portugal, and what correspondences do they exhibit with the economic and cultural investments registered by Portuguese municipalities during 2024?* Understanding the spatial distribution of PM_{2.5} in relation to economic and cultural investments across subnational administrative units is essential for informing policy frameworks aimed at reducing environmental inequalities, protecting public health, and opening new avenues of inquiry into the social cost of PM emissions.

2. Methodology

2.1. Area of Interest.

This study focuses on the 308 municipalities of Portugal, encompassing both continental territories and the autonomous island regions of Madeira and the Azores. Although Portugal is not among the most polluted countries in terms of PM_{2.5} levels, it presents a distinctive profile within the European context. Portugal displays a pattern of structural divergence typical of the Eurozone periphery, combining economic modernisation in coastal centres with persistent vulnerabilities in interior regions (World Bank Group 2019; Myrodiás 2024). The country's territory is marked by a wide diversity of economic and cultural configurations. It includes industrial and post-industrial urban areas, as well as rural zones shaped by agriculture, tourism, and artisanal economies, besides the presence of UNESCO World Heritage sites, extensive natural parks, and a vibrant cultural sector (Ramos and Carvalho 2021; Pereira and Siblot 2017). Furthermore, Portugal's decentralised municipal structure, combined with the availability of detailed socioeconomic data from national statistics (INE-PT 2022), enables a fine-grained, municipality-level analysis.

2.2 Data and Analysis.

All municipal-level socioeconomic data used in this study were obtained from statistical sheets published by the National Statistics Institute of Portugal (Instituto Nacional de Estatística, INE)—specifically the Municipal Sheet – Socioeconomic and Environmental Context (*Ficha Municipal, Contexto Socioeconómico e Ambiental*, CSE) and its companion series Information

Return to Respondents (*Retorno de Informação aos Respondentes*)—available through the INE Municipal Data Portal (*Portal de Dados Municipais do INE*) (“INE-PT” 2025). Because 2024 constitutes the most recent year with fully consolidated and publicly available municipal account data, all investment indicators were extracted for that year. This temporal delimitation aligns with the assumption—supported by institutional practice—that municipal economic and cultural investments exhibit structural inertia and are shaped by programmatic planning cycles rather than short-term fluctuations (“CNC” 2025; “CFP” 2025). These sources systematically compile and harmonise key demographic, economic, educational, and cultural indicators for each of Portugal’s 308 municipalities (Table 1). Each indicator is accompanied by detailed metadata and technical notes, ensuring comparability and reliability at the municipal scale (“INE-PT” 2025).

Table 1. Considered variables, abbreviations, investment dimensions, and definitions.

Variable	Abbrev.	Dimension	INE definition
Gross value added (million €)	GVA	Economic	Value of goods + services produced minus intermediate consumption (official “Valor acrescentado bruto”).
Business turnover (million €)	BizVol	Economic	Total value of sales of goods and services (“Volume de negócios”) realised during the reference year.
Number of firms (registered units)	Firms	Economic	Count of active enterprises recorded in the Statistical Business Register.
Newly registered legal entities (annual)	NewEnt	Economic	Annual number of newly incorporated collective persons (companies, cooperatives, etc.).
Tourism revenue (thousand €)	TourRev	Economic	Receipts from accommodation and related tourist services reported by municipalities.
Median housing price (€/m ²)	HousePrice	Economic	Median €/m ² of dwellings transacted, based on notarised deeds (<i>Estatísticas de preços da habitação</i>).
Per-capita cultural expenditure (€/inh.)	CultExp	Cultural	Municipal budget outlay on culture divided by resident population.
Library & archives expenditure (thousand €)	LibExp	Cultural	Municipal spending on libraries and archival services.
Performing-arts expenditure (thousand €)	ArtsExp	Cultural	Municipal spending on music, theatre, dance and related live-performance activities.
Gross secondary-education enrolment rate (%)	SecEnroll	Cultural	Ratio of students enrolled in secondary education to the resident population of the official age group.
Secondary-education completion rate (%)	SecCompl	Cultural	Share of students completing secondary schooling within the expected period.
Inverse basic-education dropout rate (%)	InvDrop	Cultural	100 – (dropout + retention rate) in compulsory basic education.

Capital competencies are a fundamental reality of contemporary societies, shaping the spatial distribution of resources, power, and influence across localised social spaces. From a

relational sociological perspective, the main disputed elements are economic and cultural capital (Bourdieu 1989, 1990, 2015; Gomez and Miño 2020; Gomez 2021), both operationalised through composite indicators of economic and cultural investments at the municipal level. Following this approach, and based on tests of completeness, discriminative power, and conceptual relevance, a final set of variables was selected for analysis (Table 1).

In turn, surface-level concentrations of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) were obtained from the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) Near-Real-Time (NRT) reanalysis produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) (EU/ESA/Copernicus 2024). This global product assimilates satellite retrievals and ground-based observations into a chemistry–transport model to deliver sub-daily fields of atmospheric composition at $\sim 0.4^\circ$ (~ 40 km) resolution, with a latency of only a few days. All scenes covering the period January 2019–March 2025 were accessed and processed in the Google Earth Engine cloud environment. Monthly and annual means were subsequently computed and spatially averaged within the official boundaries of Portugal’s 308 municipalities (ADM2 level), yielding a harmonised panel dataset of PM_{2.5} that is directly comparable across localities and over time.

To investigate the relationship between PM_{2.5} concentrations and the socioeconomic configurations of Portuguese municipalities, a multistage multivariate statistical analysis was conducted.

(1) It was first compiled a database of annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations for each of Portugal’s 308 municipalities for the period 2019–2025, using satellite-derived estimates. Subsequently, we applied an unsupervised classification to the temporal trajectories of PM_{2.5} across municipalities using k-means clustering. Specifically, the monthly PM_{2.5} time series for each municipality were arranged into an $n \times t$ matrix (308 municipalities \times 75 months) and subsequently standardised using z-scores (mean = 0, standard deviation = 1) in order to ensure comparability of trajectory shapes regardless of absolute levels. We then employed the KMeans clustering algorithm, a partition-based method that groups observations according to their similarity in the multivariate temporal space.

Temporal clustering techniques such as k-means are commonly employed in environmental studies to detect hidden regularities and groupings in longitudinal pollution data (Espinoza-Guillen et al. 2025; Choi, Ho, and Lee 2024). This method offers a preliminary classification that facilitates the subsequent examination of systematic correspondences between divergent pollution trajectories and the internal configurations of municipal investment—particularly in terms of annual economic and cultural investments. To preserve interpretability while retaining the municipalities most representative of each trajectory class, we selected from the latent classes trajectories database, a subsample of $n=29$ municipalities to be analysed in greater detail in the subsequent phase. To select them, municipalities within each trajectory class were ranked by their Euclidean distance to the class centroid in PM_{2.5} multivariate space, and the closest decile was retained (Class 1: 9 municipalities; Class 2: 10 municipalities; Class 3: 10 municipalities). The one-unit deviation from the theoretical 30-municipality sample reflects both rounding and a constraint imposed to ensure district-level diversity, limiting selection to one municipality per administrative district within each class.

(2) To further investigate the association between PM_{2.5} exposure and municipal characteristics, we merged the subsample of municipalities representing PM_{2.5} trajectory classes (2019–2025) with municipal indicators from the 2024 INE-CSE data sheets (“INE-PT” 2025). The economic and cultural investment data refer exclusively to the year 2024—the

most recent and complete municipal records available. Rather than a limitation, this decision is based on the relative stability of these variables over time. Unlike the short-term volatility characteristic of atmospheric conditions, municipal investments are typically guided by medium- and long-term planning cycles, embedded in political agendas, regional development strategies, and funding frameworks.

A Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) was then conducted on a targeted set of economic, cultural, and demographic variables, together with the PM2.5 trajectory classes of representative municipalities. MCA is a multivariate method suited to datasets composed primarily of categorical variables. It projects the units of analysis—a sample of 29 municipalities in this case—into a low-dimensional factorial space defined by principal axes of variation, thereby revealing proximities, oppositions, and underlying structural patterns. MCA is particularly valuable because it provides a geometric representation of social space based on the distribution of economic and cultural capital/dimensions (Lebaron and Le Roux 2018; Le Roux, Bienaise, and Durand 2021). Active variables and categories in the MCA were selected iteratively, prioritising those with the highest contributions to total inertia; supplementary variables and categories were projected passively, allowing them to appear in the geometric space without influencing the factorial solution (table 1 and 2). An expanded description of the main active and supplementary variables is available on the website of the Portuguese National Statistical Institute (“INE-PT” 2025), and in the online methodological workflow of the article.

To refine the typology of Portuguese municipalities beyond the initial factorial dimensions of the MCA, a mixed classification procedure was applied, integrating both geometric and hierarchical approaches. The procedure began with the generation of pre-partitions—small, proximity-based clusters within the MCA space—which were subsequently processed through hierarchical agglomerative clustering to produce a dendrogram that successively merged the most similar clusters. The resulting final classification reveals emergent profiles of economic investment and PM2.5 emissions, including municipalities that not only occupy similar positions in the factorial space but also share consistent multi-dimensional configurations.

Table 2. Active variables and categories of the MCA.

Active variables and categories	Description
GVA_cat	Municipal gross value added (GVA), classified in three levels (million €).
GVA_High	Upper-tercile level of GVA.
GVA_Med	Middle-tercile level of GVA.
GVA_Low	Lower-tercile level of GVA.
Turnover_cat	Municipal business turnover, classified in three levels (million €).
Turnover_High	Upper-tercile turnover.
Turnover_Med	Middle-tercile turnover.
Turnover_Low	Lower-tercile turnover.
Employees_cat	Persons employed in local economic units (<i>peçoal ao serviço</i>), classified in three levels.
Empl_High	Upper-tercile employment head-count.
Empl_Med	Middle-tercile employment head-count.

Empl_Low	Lower-tercile employment head-count.
InvDrpB_cat	Inverse basic-education dropout rate (100 – dropout & retention %), classified in three levels.
InvDrpB_High	Upper-tercile inverse rate → very few dropouts.
InvDrpB_Med	Middle-tercile inverse rate.
InvDrpB_Low	Lower-tercile inverse rate → many dropouts.
TourRev_cat	Municipal tourism revenue, classified in two levels (thousand €).
TourRev_High	Upper-tercile tourism revenue.
TourRev_Low	Lower-tercile tourism revenue.
Hotels_cat	Accommodation capacity (number of tourist establishments), classified in two levels.
Hotels_High	Upper-tercile accommodation capacity.
Hotels_Low	Lower-tercile accommodation capacity.
CultExp_cat	Per-capita municipal cultural expenditure, classified in three levels (€/inhabitant).
CultExp_High	Upper-tercile cultural expenditure per capita.
CultExp_Med	Middle-tercile cultural expenditure per capita.
CultExp_Low	Lower-tercile cultural expenditure per capita.
HerExp_cat	Per-capita municipal heritage expenditure, classified in three levels (€/inhabitant).
HerExp_High	Upper-tercile heritage expenditure.
HerExp_Med	Middle-tercile heritage expenditure.
HerExp_Low	Lower-tercile heritage expenditure.
LibExp_cat	Per-capita municipal library & archive expenditure, classified in two levels (€/inhabitant).
LibExp_High	Upper-tercile library/archive expenditure.
LibExp_Low	Lower-tercile library/archive expenditure.
PerfArt_cat	Per-capita municipal performing-arts expenditure, classified in two levels (€/inhabitant).
PerfArt_High	Upper-tercile performing-arts expenditure.
PerfArt_Low	Lower-tercile performing-arts expenditure.
InterExp_cat	Municipal expenditure on interdisciplinary cultural activities (e.g., cross-domain festivals, integrated arts events; thousand €)
InterExp_High	Upper-tercile interdisciplinary-activities expenditure
InterExp_Med	Middle-tercile interdisciplinary-activities expenditure
InterExp_Low	Lower-tercile interdisciplinary-activities expenditure.

Table 3. Supplementary variables and categories of the MCA.

Supp.variables and categories	Description
classes	PM2.5 trajectory class assigned by k-means clustering
traj1	PM2.5 trajectory class
traj2	PM2.5 trajectory class
traj3	PM2.5 trajectory class

Male cat	Male population proportion (categorised)			
Male_High	Upper-tercile (categorised)	Male	population	proportion
Male_Low	Lower-tercile (categorised)	Male	population	proportion
Male_Med	Middle-tercile (categorised)	Male	population	proportion
Female cat	Female population proportion (categorised)			
Fem_High	Upper-tercile (categorised)	Female	population	proportion
Fem_Low	Lower-tercile (categorised)	Female	population	proportion
Fem_Med	Middle-tercile (categorised)	Female	population	proportion
Children cat	Children (0–14) population share (categorised)			
PopU15_High	Upper-tercile (categorised)	Children (0–14)	population	share
PopU15_Low	Lower-tercile (categorised)	Children (0–14)	population	share
PopU15_Med	Middle-tercile (categorised)	Children (0–14)	population	share
Older adults cat	Older adults (65+) population share (categorised)			
Pop65P_High	Upper-tercile (categorised)	Older adults (65+)	population	share
Pop65P_Low	Lower-tercile (categorised)	Older adults (65+)	population	share
Pop65P_Med	Middle-tercile (categorised)	Older adults (65+)	population	share
Dens Pop cat	Population density (categorised)			
Dens_High	Upper-tercile (categorised)	Population	density	(categorised)
Dens_Low	Lower-tercile (categorised)	Population	density	(categorised)
Dens_Med	Middle-tercile (categorised)	Population	density	(categorised)
Municipality	Municipalities			
Alcoutim, Amadora, Batalha, Cadaval, Cantanhede, Carrazeda De Ansiães, Esposende, Estremoz, Fundão, Mação, Mealhada, Melgaço, Moita, Montijo, Mortágua, Moura, Nisa, Nordeste, Odemira, Oliveira Do Hospital, Penedono, Ponte De Sor, Portimão, Santa Cruz, Santarém, Trancoso, Valpaços, Vendas Novas, Vila Do Conde.				
Distritos	Districts			
Aveiro, Azores, Beja, Braga, Bragança, Castelo Branco, Coimbra, Évora, Faro, Guarda, Leiria, Lisboa, Madeira, Portalegre, Porto, Santarém, Setúbal, Viana Do Castelo, Vila Real, Viseu.				

In the mixed classification, to delineate the main dimensions of the MCA and to construct homogeneous groups of municipalities, we retained the first ten axes—which together account for 94.14 % of the total inertia—and used their coordinates as input for an agglomerative hierarchical clustering (table 3). Although all ten axes were considered in the clustering step,

the first factorial plane (Axes 1—2) alone captures 50 % of the inertia and reveals the most salient opposition—high economic capital versus high cultural investment—central to our relational perspective (table 3). Subsequent axes contribute statistically meaningful yet secondary nuances that do not modify the core spatial configuration. Accordingly, the interpretation in the text concentrates on Axes 1 and 2, while results for Axes 3—5 are provided in the online supplementary data for completeness.

Table 4. Panel of Eigenvalues. Trace of matrix: 1.75947

Axis	Eigenvalue	Percentage	Cumulated Percentage
1	0.5129	29.15	29.15
2	0.3672	20.87	50.02
3	0.1621	9.21	59.23
4	0.1490	8.47	67.70
5	0.1201	6.83	74.53
6	0.1023	5.82	80.35
7	0.0738	4.19	84.54
8	0.0663	3.77	88.31
9	0.0592	3.36	91.67
10	0.0434	2.47	94.14
11	0.0347	1.97	96.11
12	0.0239	1.36	97.47
13	0.0198	1.13	98.60
14	0.0115	0.66	99.25
15	0.0092	0.52	99.78
16	0.0039	0.22	100.00

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Trajectory classes of PM2.5

How are the temporal trajectories of PM2.5 exposure (2019—2025) spatially distributed across Portugal?. To identify latent patterns in the temporal evolution of fine particulate matter (PM2.5) across Portuguese municipalities from 2019 to 2025, we applied an unsupervised time-series clustering technique on monthly average pollution values. The result is a typology of latent trajectories, where each class captures a distinct pattern in the temporal dynamics of air pollution at the municipal level (figure 1).

Figure 1. Typology of Average Annual PM2.5 Trajectories. January 2019 to April 2025.

Between 2019 and 2020, all classes experienced a marked decline in PM2.5 concentrations, reflecting reduced industrial and transportation activities, largely attributable to COVID-19 lockdowns and a temporary drop in anthropogenic emissions (figure 1). From 2020 onward, levels began to rise again with notable fluctuations, especially in high pollution trajectories (Traj 3), coinciding with economic reopening and resumed pollution sources. Throughout the period, all classes showed synchronized seasonal patterns, indicating that meteorological and climatic factors such as temperature inversions, humidity, and wind strongly influence PM2.5 dispersion and accumulation nationwide (Alam, Karim, and Zaman 2025). In summary, the three identified classes of trajectories represent distinct pollution profiles with differing mean levels and variability.

Class 1 – Low Pollution Trajectories. This class includes the municipalities with mean PM2.5 values ranging approximately from 5.44 to 6.85 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and coefficients of variation (CV) ranging from about 0.28 to 0.43, indicating moderate variability in pollution levels. Examples include Trancoso (Guarda) with 5.75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (CV 0.39), Moura (Beja) with 6.00 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (CV 0.32), and Melgaço (Viana do Castelo) with 6.27 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (CV 0.43) (table 5). These municipalities tend to have relatively low PM2.5 concentrations and moderate internal dispersion, typically associated with less urbanised or industrialised areas.

Class 2 – Intermediate Pollution Trajectories. This class comprises municipalities with mean PM2.5 concentrations approximately between 6.70 and 8.10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and CV values ranging roughly from 0.24 to 0.33. Representative municipalities include Batalha (Leiria) at 7.78 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (CV 0.27), Cantanhede (Coimbra) at 8.10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (CV 0.30), and Montijo (Setúbal) at 7.50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (CV 0.25) (table 5). This range reflects an intermediate pollution level with relatively lower internal variation compared to Class 1.

Class 3 – High Pollution Trajectories. This group features municipalities with higher PM2.5 concentrations, from about 8.63 up to 11.07 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with CV values approximately between 0.25 and 0.37. Municipalities such as Amadora (Lisboa) with 9.97 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (CV 0.26), Esposende (Braga) with 10.64 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (CV 0.25), and Vila do Conde (Porto) with 11.07 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (CV 0.25) exemplify this class (table 5). These municipalities show consistently elevated PM2.5 values with moderate internal variability, often linked to highly urbanised or industrialised areas.

Figure 2. Typology of Average Monthly PM2.5. January 2019 to April 2025

The intra-annual dynamics of air pollution between 2019 and 2025, based on a seasonal analysis of PM_{2.5} mean annual concentrations, reveal similarities and differences across the three classes (Figure 2).

Trajectory 1, the least polluted, shows a stable but cyclical pattern with a modest peak in March (7.2 µg/m³) and a decline in late autumn and early winter, reaching a minimum in November (4.5 µg/m³). This pattern suggests sensitivity to seasonal emissions, likely from heating or biomass burning.

Trajectory 2, moderately polluted, has a pronounced peak in February (9.0 µg/m³) followed by a steady decline to August (7.1 µg/m³), and a secondary peak in September (9.8 µg/m³), possibly due to post-summer atmospheric inversions or delayed emissions.

Trajectory 3, the most polluted, maintains high and stable PM_{2.5} levels with a peak in February (11.7 µg/m³) and a secondary peak in September (10.0 µg/m³). This indicates persistent structural pollution from industrial or vehicular sources. The decline in classes 2 and 3 from May to August likely reflects reduced emissions during summer holidays and favorable meteorological conditions that enhance pollutant dispersion. Overall, seasonal effects are evident in all classes, but their timing and intensity vary. These variations underscore the need for seasonally adaptive mitigation strategies tailored to the specific temporal pollution profiles of different regions.

The cartographic rendering of the three latent trajectory classes (Figure 3) discloses the tripartite geography of PM_{2.5} dynamics that cuts across Portugal's administrative mosaic. A broad, quasi-continuous belt of **Class 1 trajectory (blue)** extends from the high-relief Minho-Trás-os-Montes frontier through the Beira and Alto Alentejo interiors to the Guadiana valley, epitomising trajectories characterised by persistently low background concentrations and muted seasonal amplitudes. Flanking this inland core, a discontinuous **Class 2 littoral corridor trajectory (orange)** follows the main Atlantic urban–industrial axis from the Aveiro lagoon to the Sado and lower Guadiana estuaries; here, moderate baseline levels combine with pronounced winter–summer contrasts that mirror the rhythm of coastal traffic, port activity and heating demand. Finally, **Class 3 enclaves trajectory (green)** punctuate the map in three strategic settings: (i) the autonomous archipelagos of Madeira and the Azores, where marine aerosol, shipping plumes and episodic Saharan dust generate sharp but short-lived peaks; (ii) selected tourism-intensive tracts of the Algarve and western Alentejo littoral; and (iii) port-industrial conurbations such as Porto-Leixões and Setúbal. Taken together, the spatial pattern captures distinct temporal signatures rather than a simple gradient of pollution magnitude, and underscores the relational premise that divergent PM_{2.5} trajectories must be analysed in relation to the differentiated economic and cultural investment profiles of municipalities.

Figure 3. Distribution of PM2.5 trajectory classes in Portugal (2019—2025).

To select a representative subset, approximately 10% of the municipalities closest to each trajectory class centroid in PM2.5 space were chosen, ensuring that no two municipalities from the same administrative district (NAME_1) were included. This strategy guarantees that the selected sample accurately represents the typical PM2.5 exposure patterns characteristic of each cluster, and preserves geographic diversity by avoiding redundancy within districts (table 4).

Table 5. Selected representatives municipalities of PM2.5 by trajectory classes.

MUNICIPIO_ID	NAME_1	class	mean_pm25	cv_pm25
Trancoso (Guarda)	Guarda	1	5.753121	0.385091
Penedono (Viseu)	Viseu	1	5.949848	0.413845
Fundão (Castelo Branco)	Castelo Branco	1	6.205403	0.359353
Oliveira do Hospital (Coimbra)	Coimbra	1	6.543970	0.349714
Valpaços (Vila Real)	Vila Real	1	5.809820	0.401057
Carraceda de Ansiães (Bragança)	Bragança	1	5.441534	0.368988
Nisa (Portalegre)	Portalegre	1	6.420625	0.290337

Estremoz (Évora)	Évora	1	6.282494	0.288777
Mação (Santarém)	Santarém	1	6.848363	0.283500
Moura (Beja)	Beja	1	5.996860	0.316643
Melgaço (Viana do Castelo)	Viana do Castelo	1	6.272007	0.432637
Alcoutim (Faro)	Faro	1	6.516323	0.294728
Batalha (Leiria)	Leiria	2	7.778669	0.267184
Santarém (Santarém)	Santarém	2	7.624499	0.243763
Cadaval (Lisboa)	Lisboa	2	8.091333	0.237724
Mortágua (Viseu)	Viseu	2	7.868129	0.314529
Cantanhede (Coimbra)	Coimbra	2	8.104945	0.302071
Mealhada (Aveiro)	Aveiro	2	7.601800	0.327078
Montijo (Setúbal)	Setúbal	2	7.501571	0.253616
Ponte de Sôr (Portalegre)	Portalegre	2	6.703244	0.264534
Odemira (Beja)	Beja	2	7.205290	0.265516
Vendas Novas (Évora)	Évora	2	6.745696	0.266541
Moita (Setúbal)	Setúbal	3	9.394950	0.252603
Amadora (Lisboa)	Lisboa	3	9.966470	0.256918
Portimão (Faro)	Faro	3	9.181091	0.267180
Esposende (Braga)	Braga	3	10.643280	0.246694
Nordeste (Azores)	Azores	3	9.423650	0.347062
Santa Cruz (Madeira)	Madeira	3	8.626807	0.365447
Vila do Conde (Porto)	Porto	3	11.071163	0.252238

In summary, the municipalities selected by PM2.5 trajectory classes exhibit distinct annual mean concentrations consistent with the seasonal patterns observed in the monthly and annual analysis. Class 1 includes municipalities with the lowest average PM2.5 levels, generally between 5.4 and 6.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and exhibits higher temporal variability. Class 2 corresponds to moderate exposure levels, ranging from about 6.7 to 8.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with less variation over time. Class 3 gathers municipalities with the highest pollution, between approximately 8.6 and 11.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, where concentrations remain relatively stable throughout the year. The selected municipalities cover diverse districts and regions, reflecting spatial

heterogeneity in pollution exposure across Portugal, and providing a practical basis for combining environmental and socioeconomic data at the municipal level.

3.2. Correspondences Between Municipal Investment and PM2.5 Trajectories

What is the relationship between PM2.5 exposure trends (2019–2025) and the 2024 economic and cultural investments in key Portuguese municipalities? The three trajectory classes derived in Section 3.1 serve as categorical supplementary inputs, alongside key economic and cultural active variables (Tables 1 and 2), for a Multiple Correspondence Analysis and subsequent Mixed Clustering. This integrated approach enables a joint exploration of particulate-exposure dynamics and municipal investment patterns. In the analysis, when the first two axes of the MCA are read together, they delineate an interpretable socio-economic plane: the horizontal dimension ranks municipalities by the intensity and diversity of capital investment, while the vertical dimension discriminates between tourism-oriented and culturally under-financed municipalities (table 6 and figure 4).

Table 6. Relative weight, distance to origin, contributions, and squared correlations for the first two factorial axes.

Label	Relative Weight	Distance to origin	Contr 1	Contr 2	Cos ² 1	Cos ² 2
GVA cat						
GVA_High	3.762	1.41642	9.03	0.02	0.87	0.00
GVA_Low	3.398	1.67533	4.56	7.54	0.41	0.49
GVA_Med	3.034	1.99636	2.10	9.91	0.18	0.60
Turnover cat						
Turnover_High	3.762	1.41642	7.51	0.11	0.72	0.01
Turnover_Low	3.398	1.67533	4.85	9.57	0.44	0.62
Turnover_Med	3.034	1.99636	1.19	9.02	0.10	0.55
Employees cat						
Empl_High	3.803	1.39072	8.77	0.02	0.85	0.00
Empl_Low	3.317	1.74058	3.35	9.07	0.30	0.58
Empl_Med	3.074	1.95694	3.04	9.55	0.26	0.58
InvDrpB_cat						
InvDrpB_High	3.236	1.80909	2.54	0.05	0.22	0.00
InvDrpB_Low	3.479	1.61311	0.14	2.10	0.01	0.14
InvDrpB_Med	3.155	1.88112	1.73	2.95	0.15	0.18
TourRev_cat						
TourRev_High	3.843	1.36555	5.36	1.36	0.52	0.10
TourRev_Low	3.600	1.52503	4.17	4.26	0.39	0.29
Hotels_cat						
Hotels_High	3.277	1.77441	0.43	4.21	0.04	0.27
Hotels_Low	3.681	1.46953	0.91	2.32	0.09	0.16
CultExp_cat						
CultExp_High	3.762	1.41642	5.99	0.84	0.58	0.06
CultExp_Low	3.358	1.70756	5.08	6.20	0.45	0.40
CultExp_Med	3.074	1.95694	0.52	2.36	0.04	0.14

HerExp_cat						
HerExp_High	3.681	1.46953	3.34	0.68	0.32	0.05
HerExp_Low	3.398	1.67533	0.42	6.50	0.04	0.42
HerExp_Med	3.115	1.91854	2.93	2.91	0.25	0.18
LibExp_cat						
LibExp_High	3.641	1.49697	6.17	0.04	0.58	0.00
LibExp_Low	3.560	1.55372	1.97	0.22	0.18	0.01
PerfArt_cat						
PerfArt_High	3.843	1.36555	3.28	2.65	0.32	0.19
PerfArt_Low	3.519	1.58307	0.69	3.93	0.06	0.26
InterExp_cat						
InterExp_High	3.681	1.46953	5.21	0.72	0.49	0.05
InterExp_Low	3.398	1.67533	4.16	0.00	0.37	0.00
InterExp_Med	3.115	1.91854	0.55	0.88	0.05	0.05

The first factorial axis of the MCA is dominated by categories that embody dense stocks of economic and cultural capital, *GVA_High*, *Empl_High*, and *Turnover_High* each contribute between 7.5 % and 9 % to the axis and display squared correlations (Cos^2) above 0.70, while *LibExp_High*, *CultExp_High*, and *InterExp_High* add a further 5–6 % apiece with Cos^2 values around 0.50. Taken together, these figures indicate that municipalities situated at the positive end of Axis 1 combine high gross value added, large employment bases, and vigorous turnover with above-average investments in libraries, cultural programming, and intercultural services. At the opposite pole lie the medium- and low-level counterparts of these variables, whose more modest contributions nonetheless locate them firmly on the negative side. Axis 1 therefore traces a clear gradient of aggregate economic-and-cultural capital, separating capital-rich, culture-investing hubs from fiscally constrained settings.

The second axis is structured by a different configuration. The strongest contributors—*GVA_Med*, *Turnover_Med*, *Empl_Med*, *Turnover_Low*, and *Empl_Low*—each account for roughly 9 % of the axis, with Cos^2 values of 0.55–0.60, signalling municipalities that combine moderate or low productive output with limited labour absorption. These same cases also align with *CultExp_Low* and *HerExp_Low*, both of which add more than 6 % to the axis and exhibit Cos^2 near 0.40, pointing to chronic under-investment in cultural and heritage sectors. Anchoring the opposite direction is *Hotels_High*, whose 4 % contribution ($\text{Cos}^2 \approx 0.27$) denotes localities that offset weak productive industries with high-capacity accommodation infrastructure; *TourRev_High* follows a similar, though weaker pattern. Axis 2 thus opposes tourism-service specialisation to cultural under-investment coupled with modest economic throughput, revealing two distinct development strategies within the lower-to-mid tier of the Portuguese municipal economy.

Figure 4. MCA and mixed clustering on main economic and cultural investments of municipalities, and PM2.5 trajectories from 2019 to 2025.

Following the MCA, the mixed classification procedure yielded three distinct clusters of municipalities, each associated with a specific configuration of economic, cultural, and PM2.5 attributes. The analysis of annual mean PM2.5 values across these groups reveals statistically significant differences (Fisher = 7.41, $p = 0.003$ for 2021; Fisher = 5.76, $p = 0.008$ for 2024), confirming that long-term exposure to particulate matter aligns with distinct socio-spatial profiles.

Cluster 1 – *Peripheral Low-Capital Municipalities*. Comprising ten predominantly rural or interior municipalities, this cluster is marked by the lowest recorded PM2.5 exposure levels in the dataset ($6.61 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2021 and $6.60 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2024), suggesting a relatively unpolluted atmospheric environment. Statistically, it is characterised by universal presence in the *Turnover_Low* category (100% of municipalities) and a 90% incidence of *Employees_Low*, denoting weak productive infrastructure and reduced labour absorption capacity. Further distinguishing features include minimal cultural spending and low Gross Value Added, both of which reflect structural constraints in the economic and institutional fabric of these municipalities. The overlapping of low turnover and limited employment reinforces the cluster’s identification with peripheral territories displaying weak fiscal capacity, modest diversification of economic functions, and limited industrial or service-based activity. From a relational perspective, these same characteristics likely contribute to the reduced intensity of anthropogenic emissions, which in turn explain their comparatively cleaner air. Their marginal positioning within the national economic space—amplified by structural inertia in investment and reduced integration into broader cultural circuits—suggests that these municipalities may be doubly disadvantaged: structurally insulated from both pollution and investment flows.

Table 8. Main characteristics of Cluster 1 municipalities.

CLUSTER 1 / 3 (Count: 10 Municipalities - Percentage: 34.48)			
Characteristic categories	% of category in group	% of category in set	Test-value

Turnover_Low	100.00	34.48	5.33
Empl_Low	90.00	34.48	4.28
GVA_Low	90.00	34.48	4.28
PopU15_Low	90.00	34.48	4.28
Pop65P_Low	80.00	34.48	3.36
Fem_Low	80.00	34.48	3.36
Male_Low	80.00	34.48	3.36
TourRev_Low	70.00	34.48	2.50
Dens_Low	70.00	34.48	2.50

Cluster 2 – *Intermediate-Capital. Moderately Exposed Municipalities*. Comprising eight municipalities, predominantly situated in peri-urban belts or semi-integrated zones adjacent to metropolitan cores. These municipalities register intermediate PM2.5 exposure values—7.34 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2021 and 7.60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2024—positioning them between the structurally peripheral and the heavily urbanised profiles. The cluster is characterised by modal economic categories such as *GVA_Med* and *Empl_Med*, indicating moderate productive intensity and employment capacity. These municipalities maintain functional but non-dominant economic structures, often combining modest manufacturing with localised service provision. Their cultural expenditure is systematically low (*CultExp_Low*), suggesting that while economic functionality exists, cultural investment remains underdeveloped or residual. These municipalities tend to operate as transition zones: more economically active than rural peripheries but not structurally embedded in high-capital or high-density networks. Consequently, while their industrial and traffic intensities exceed those of Cluster 1, they remain insufficient to propel PM2.5 levels into the upper exposure tier observed in Cluster 3. This liminal positioning—economically functional yet infrastructurally constrained—makes Cluster 2 particularly relevant for policy interventions aiming at both air quality improvements and strategic reinforcement of cultural and economic capacities.

Table 9. Main characteristics of Cluster 2 municipalities.

CLUSTER 2 / 3 (Count: 8 Municipalities - Percentage: 27.59)			
Characteristic categories	% of category in group	% of category in set	Test-value
Turnover_Med	87.50	31.03	3.58
GVA_Med	87.50	31.03	3.58
Empl_Med	87.50	31.03	3.58
CultExp_Low	87.50	34.48	3.27
PopU15_Med	75.00	31.03	2.66
HerExp_Low	75.00	34.48	2.37

Cluster 3 – *High-Capital. High-Exposure Municipalities*. Encompassing eleven municipalities located predominantly along the Portuguese coast and within major metropolitan areas. These municipalities exhibit the highest recorded levels of PM2.5 in the dataset—9.26 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2021 and 9.13 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2024—surpassing both the national average and WHO recommended thresholds—5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (annual mean)— (“WHO” 2024). Their elevated particulate burden aligns closely with their role as nodes of intensified capital circulation and accumulation. Economically, the cluster is marked by a strong incidence of *Turnover_Med* and *GVA_Med* categories (87.5%), reflecting substantial volumes of economic activity and value

generation. While not strictly in the "high" categories, these medium levels reflect the dense concentration of industrial, logistical, and commercial functions typically found in urban coastal settings. These territories also concentrate hotel infrastructure and cultural expenditure, pointing to an active tourist economy and significant municipal investment in cultural assets. The socioeconomic profile of these municipalities suggests a double bind: they act both as economic engines—hosting diversified production and high service-sector turnover—and as tourist and cultural hubs, with significant daily influxes of visitors. This combination generates a cumulative emissions profile shaped by road traffic, industrial activity, and energy consumption linked to service infrastructure. The environmental consequence of this dual role is a consistent elevation in PM2.5 exposure levels, which, unlike in peripheral areas, cannot be mitigated solely through passive factors such as low density or geographic isolation. Instead, they highlight a structural contradiction: the very assets that underpin local prosperity—economic complexity, connectivity, and cultural vibrancy—also intensify their exposure to atmospheric degradation.

Table 10. Main characteristics of Cluster 3 municipalities.

Group: CLUSTER 3 / 3 (Count: 11 Municipalities - Percentage: 37.93)			
Characteristic categories	% of category in group	% of category in set	Test-value
GVA_High	90.91	34.48	4.87
Pop65P_High	81.82	34.48	3.89
PopU15_High	81.82	34.48	3.89
Fem_High	81.82	34.48	3.89
Turnover_High	81.82	34.48	3.89
Empl_High	81.82	34.48	3.89
Male_High	81.82	34.48	3.89
InterExp_High	72.73	34.48	3.01
LibExp_High	72.73	34.48	3.01
Dens_High	72.73	34.48	3.01
CultExp_High	72.73	34.48	3.01

PM2.5 trajectory classes between 2019 and 2025 were included as supplementary variables in the MCA; therefore, they did not actively shape the factorial space or influence the clustering process, as confirmed by their absence among the statistically significant categorical contributors to cluster differentiation. To further assess the alignment between air pollution dynamics and investment-based municipal profiles, it was performed a chi-square test of independence between the three PM2.5 trajectory classes and the three final socioeconomic clusters (table).

Table 11. Classes of PM2.5 trajectories and clusters of economic and cultural investments in municipalities.

Trajectory classes	Cluster 1/3	Cluster 2/3	Cluster 3/3	Total
Traj 1	8 (1.66)	3 (-0.31)	2 (-1.32)	13
Traj 2	1 (-1.19)	4 (0.96)	4 (0.32)	9
Traj 3	1 (-0.91)	1 (-0.67)	5 (1.44)	7
Total	10	8	11	29

The test revealed a statistically significant association ($\chi^2(4) = 10.40$, $p = 0.034$), indicating that PM2.5 exposure patterns are not randomly distributed across clusters. Observed frequencies and standardized residuals (in parentheses) confirm the overrepresentation of low-exposure municipalities (Traj 1) in Cluster 1/3 and high-exposure municipalities (Traj 3) in Cluster 3/3. This statistical alignment reinforces the structural correspondences initially identified through the MCA and substantiates the central presumption: that capital externalities such as PM2.5 are systematically co-produced and distributed through the spatialised composition of capital investments at the municipal level.

4. Conclusions

The findings emphasize that PM2.5 exposure in Portugal is a structured outcome of differentiated capital competences. Municipalities that concentrate economic and cultural resources—through high levels of productivity, tourism, and cultural investment—also accumulate the highest particulate burdens, revealing that air pollution is not an external aberration but a constitutive feature of capital-driven territorial development. Conversely, peripheral municipalities sustain lower PM2.5 levels primarily because structural marginality limits the scale of economic and cultural investments capable of generating significant emissions—yet this cleaner profile bifurcates: certain municipalities compensate modest productive capacity with tourism-oriented infrastructure, whereas others remain low-emitting precisely due to persistent under-investment across both sectors. By interlinking a seven-year panel of satellite-derived PM2.5 concentrations (2019—2025) with the most recent suite of municipal economic and cultural accounts (2024), the study delineates a multidimensional cartography of socio-environmental interdependence at the sub-national scale of Portugal's 308 municipalities. Summarising, the main points of the article suggest that stratified particulate burdens reflect distinct capital regimes. A triadic clustering scheme reveals that municipalities rich in both productive and cultural capital—chiefly coastal and metropolitan jurisdictions—sustain the highest mean annual exposures (≈ 8.6 — $11.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), surpassing the national average and brushing World Health Organization guideline values.

At the opposite pole of high pollution areas, structurally peripheral jurisdictions register the lowest exposures to PM2.5 (≈ 5.4 — $6.8 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), a by-product of limited industrial throughput and chronically low investment across economic and cultural sectors. Municipalities classified under the low pollution trajectory class (traj1) are predominantly characterized by low economic investment variables such as low business turnover (Turnover_Low), gross value added (GVA_Low), and employment rates (Empl_Low). This limited industrial and commercial activity corresponds to lower anthropogenic emissions of PM2.5, explaining the relatively clean air quality profiles in these predominantly rural and peripheral areas. Nonetheless, this apparent environmental advantage is intrinsically tied to structural marginality and limited socioeconomic opportunities, indicating that clean air in these settings emerges more from economic underdevelopment rather than from proactive environmental management.

Intermediate municipalities occupy a liminal position where moderate but rising concentrations (≈ 6.7 — $8.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) coincide with middling investment profiles, accentuating their susceptibility to policy intervention. A chi-square test corroborates the non-random alignment between these pollution profiles and the three investment clusters ($\chi^2 = 10.40$, $p = 0.034$). Intermediate pollution trajectory municipalities (traj2), often situated in semi-urban or transitional areas, reveal moderate economic investments primarily focused on mid-level gross value added (GVA_Med), business turnover (Turnover_Med), and employment figures (Empl_Med). Cultural investment remains significantly low (CultExp_Low), highlighting an

investment strategy emphasizing moderate economic functionality without strong support for cultural and educational development. These municipalities reflect vulnerability due to their intermediate positioning, suggesting potential susceptibility to increasing pollution pressures as they expand industrial and urban activities without adequate cultural or environmental investment buffers.

The high pollution trajectory class (Class 3) encompasses municipalities that are economically and culturally dynamic, evidenced by high gross value added (GVA_High), employment (Empl_High), business turnover (Turnover_High), and substantial cultural investment (CultExp_High, LibExp_High, InterExp_High). These are predominantly urbanized coastal and metropolitan hubs characterized by intense industrial, logistical, and tourism activities. The dual role as economic engines and cultural-touristic centers creates a structurally embedded contradiction: economic prosperity and vibrant cultural life come at the expense of sustained high levels of PM_{2.5} exposure, significantly exceeding national averages and posing long-term public health risks.

4.1. Contributions.

Positioning municipal space as the primary analytical lens broadens ecological-economics inquiry beyond national aggregates, revealing how subnational governance and capital accumulation co-produce and spatially converge with specific environmental burdens. Secondly, by enrolling cultural expenditure—such as libraries, heritage, and performing arts budgets—as a constitutive dimension of capital competences, the research reveals an often-overlooked pathway through which environmental inequalities are either entrenched or alleviated. Finally, the mixed MCA–hierarchical clustering architecture offers a transferable template for diagnosing socio-environmental trade-offs in other decentralised settings. These findings imply that national climate and air-quality frameworks could (i) recalibrate fiscal transfer rules that allow capital-rich municipalities to externalise particulate costs, (ii) mainstream culture and education within green-transition financing, and (iii) adopt seasonally differentiated mitigation, given the pronounced winter–summer swings in high-exposure municipal clusters. Local ecological-economic accounting must therefore internalise particulate damage when appraising infrastructure and tourism-promotion initiatives.

4.2. Limitations and avenues for further research.

The atmospheric data rest on a 0.4° CAMS reanalysis product, whose coarse resolution may obscure intra-urban gradients; higher-resolution chemistry–transport modelling could refine cluster boundaries. Moreover, PM_{2.5} is a heterogeneous pollutant, composed of both anthropogenic and natural particulates—including marine aerosols and Saharan dust—which inflate concentrations in insular regions like Madeira and the Azores. Finally, extending the relational framework to other pollutants (e.g., NO₂, O₃) and to cross-border Iberian contexts would test the generalisability of municipal capital-driven externalities. Notwithstanding these methodological and spatial limitations, the findings position PM_{2.5} not as a random or exogenous hazard but as a systemic outcome of capital-driven territorial investments. This underscores the importance of ecological-economic governance strategies that are both territorially targeted and culturally responsive.

5. Ethics statements

The authors declare that no ethical conflicts exist concerning the research presented in this paper.

6. Author contributions: CRediT

Gómez Raimundo Elías: Conceptualization. Methodology. Data curation. Writing- Original draft preparation.

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